

CULTURE AND MAN.

Fayziyeva Jasmina Anvarovna

4th year student of TerDU Faculty of Foreign Philology.

Annotation: In this article, the question of culture taking an important place in a person's life, behavior of a person, manners, development of skills to understand human qualities, creation of cultural and ethical activities is realized.

Key words: human, culture, thinking, physical strength, imagination, artistic moral concepts, spirituality, human concepts.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещается вопрос о культуре, занимающей важное место в жизни человека, поведении человека, манерах, развитии умений понимать человеческие качества, создании культурно-этической деятельности.

Ключевые слова: человек, культура, мышление, физическая сила, воображение, художественные моральные концепции, духовность, человеческие концепции.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada madaniyat inson xayotida muxim o`rin egallashi insonni o`zini tutishi odob axloqiy insoniy fazilatlarini anglash malakasini rivojlantirish faoliyatini yuzaga keltirish madaniy axloqiy faoliyatlar ko`zda tutish masalasi amalga oshirilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: inson, madaniyat, fikr yuritish, jismoniy quvvat, tasavvurlar, badiiy axloqiy tushunchalar, ma`naviyat, insoniy tushunchalar.

Culture is a concept that represents the spiritual and mental world of a person. It includes people's philosophical, legal, scientific, artistic, moral, and religious ideas. At the base of the term "spirituality" is the word "meaning". It is known that there is an external and internal world of a person. The external world includes his

height, appearance, clothes, behavior, etc. His inner world includes his life purpose, thoughts, dreams, aspirations, feelings. This inner world of man is spirituality. If food gives a person physical strength, spirituality gives him spiritual nourishment and strength. Spirituality is related to enlightenment and culture. Spirituality does not arise in people by chance. It can be achieved only through constant study, learning, and experience. The richer the spirituality, the more prosperous the society and the nation. A spiritual person clearly knows the purpose of living, finds a way to spend his life meaningfully, acquires the culture of dealing, approaches every issue from the point of view of fairness and justice. Conscience can distinguish between what is false and what is true, what is honor, what is honest and what is forbidden, and it will give up actions that lead to evil in life, and perform actions that lead to good. In short, the meaning of human life is reflected in spirituality. Love of country, patriotism is one of the main factors determining human spirituality. In societies where spirituality has matured, the possessors of abilities and talents are the face, pride, and prestige of this society, the nation. In a spiritual society, reason, common sense, justice and good behavior are the priority. In such a society, the people's faith in the future will be strong, and various vices that are unbecoming to a person will disappear. It is difficult to imagine spirituality without the roots of the nation formed over the centuries, its historical experiences and socio-cultural development. "Spirituality is the strength of a person, nation, society, and state. There will never be happiness where it is not there," said the President of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov. For this reason, the promotion of spirituality in Uzbekistan has been raised to the level of state policy. Thanks to independence, a wide way has been opened to study the centuries-old rich historical, scientific, cultural and religious heritage of the Uzbek people, and to use it as a common and invaluable property of the people. Our spirituality has been formed, enriched and developed side by side with universal human values, starting from the teaching of "Avesta" and Zoroastrianism. In Uzbekistan, the Republic Center "Spirituality and

Enlightenment" was established in order to raise, promote, enrich and spread spirituality and enlightenment to a wide range of people. The subject "Fundamentals of Spirituality" is taught in the republican education system. Scientific research is being conducted in the field of spirituality.

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